

Organo-Antimony Compounds. Part IV. Stibinic Acids derived from certain Local Anaesthetics.

By SUDHIR CHANDRA NITYOGY.

Of all the substances that have been put forward as a substitute for cocaine and its allied products for the production of local anaesthesia, the derivatives of aminobenzoic acid appear to be the best. Cocaine, in spite of its intense local anaesthetic action, suffers from several disadvantages both chemical and commercial. In the first place cocaine induces "a habit" and secondly it has a distinctly injurious action on the heart. Moreover, the substance is costly and its preparation, even on a semi-commercial scale, has yet to be accomplished. The derivatives of aminobenzoic acids on the other hand do not suffer from any of these drawbacks.

Aminobenzoic acid is capable of elaboration in three directions:—

1. Esterification of the carboxyl group.
2. Substitution in the amino-group, with or without the elaboration of the ester grouping.
3. Substitution in the aromatic nucleus.

In the esterification of the carboxyl group, it has been found that the activity of the compound gradually increases up to amyl esters after which there is a falling off in the activity and that the introduction of an alkylamino-group in the alkyl ester group of aminobenzoic acid gives a compound possessing powerful local anaesthetic action.

When both the amino- and carboxyl groups of aminobenzoic acids are protected, a series of compounds are obtained of considerable activity. But the greatest drawback of this series of compounds is their insolubility in water, which however might be got over by the introduction of an acidic group.

The introduction of hydroxyl group into the nucleus of aminobenzoic acid gives a compound of about twice the anaesthetic activity but with an added antiseptic action. The simplest member

of the series is 3-oxy-4-aminobenzoic ester, whose toxicity is low and can therefore be used as a combined antiseptic and analgesic.

The next advance in this line was the fact discovered by Wichura (*Z. exp. Path. Ther.*, 7, 72) that the removal of the nuclear amino-group, does not, as might be expected, lead to the production of a compound of no local anaesthetic activity. In fact Wichura showed that benzoyl *N*-dimethylpropanol $C_6H_5COO-CH_2-CH_2-CH_2-N(CH_3)_2$ has a moderate local anaesthetic activity and a very low toxicity, which makes it perfectly safe for use. It has been found in the course of this work that benzyl benzoate possesses the property of an excellent local anaesthetic. Its therapeutic index is sufficiently high to warrant its use for the production of local anaesthesia.

An attempt has been made to prepare the six possible isomeric nitro- and amino-derivatives of benzyl benzoate with a view to obtain the corresponding stibinic acid through the diazo-reaction. The object in view is to combine, in a stibinic acid, the aggregations of groups which can give rise to local anaesthesia so that it might be of use for the treatment of Kala-azar, by intramuscular injection, without any great local irritation. Although the physiological examination of these substances has not been as thorough as ought to be, owing to the absence of co-operation between the medical profession and research workers, yet it appears that these stibinic acids are almost without action for the treatment of Kala-azar, though they possess local anaesthetic action to a certain extent.

The first step in the process is the preparation of the six possible nitro-derivatives—three of them being derived from the three nitrobenzoic acids and the rest from the three nitrobenzyl alcohols. Of these, two only appear to have been studied by previous workers. Gomberg and Buchler (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 42, 2059) has described the preparation of 2-nitrobenzyl benzoate and Bamberger and Renaud (*Ber.*, 1897, 30, 2288), benzyl 4-nitrobenzoate. The method employed by Gomberg and Buchler is remarkable in some respects. 2-Nitrobenzyl chloride and sodium benzoate in water solution were heated to 115-20° for 8—10 hours. The solid that separated on cooling, gave the pure ester on crystallisation from dilute alcohol, as a *light brown* crystalline mass, m.p. 89-90°. It has been found that when the ester is prepared by the method of Gomberg and Buchler, the m.p. of the product is 89-90°, but when the ester is prepared by any other method, it melts at 101.2° and is a white

crystalline mass. This leads one to conclude that the product obtained by the previous authors was contaminated with colouring matters, which they did not attempt to remove, because it has been further observed that the reduction products of the nitro-bodies, by entirely different methods, gave the identical amine. But the most striking feature of the method of Gomberg and Buehler is that the reaction takes place smoothly in the case of the three nitrobenzyl chlorides and sodium benzoate but fails completely when nitrobenzoic acids (sodium salts) and benzyl chlorides are employed, though a greater part of benzyl chloride appears to undergo hydrolysis. This failure in the case of the substituted benzoic acids might be due to the hydrolysis of the esters produced during the first stage of the reaction, but it is strange that in no case, a trace of the ester was obtained, even when the temperature and the period of heating were varied.

Benzyl 4-nitrobenzoate has been prepared by Bamberger and Renaud (*Ber.*, 1897, 30, 2288) by the action of 4-nitrobenzoyl chloride on benzyl alcohol. But as the preparation of 4-nitrobenzoyl chloride is a tedious operation, an easier and simpler method was considered to be necessary. The esterification of 4-nitrobenzoic acid was accomplished by simply heating an equimolecular quantity of the acid and benzyl alcohol to 160-80° for 4-5 hours. But attempts to prepare benzyl 3-nitrobenzoate by this method were unsuccessful. The usual method of the preparation of esters (by the action of dry hydrochloric or sulphuric acid upon the acid and alcohol) proved to be useless. On heating silver 3-nitrobenzoate and benzyl chloride in dry benzene suspension, no definite product was obtained. 3-Nitrobenzoyl chloride and benzyl alcohol, by the Schöitten-Baumann reaction, gave the anhydride of 3-nitrobenzoic acid. Similar was the case with 2-nitrobenzoic acid, the silver salt of which was found to be soluble in water. As in the case of 4-nitrobenzoic acid, it was found that when an equimolecular quantity of 2-nitrobenzoic acid and benzyl alcohol was heated to 140-60° for 8-10 hours, the ester was formed in some cases but the results were not uniform, as in most cases an oil was obtained from which it was found impossible to separate the ester. The esterification of 2-nitro- and 3-nitro-benzoic acids was smoothly accomplished by allowing the corresponding acid chlorides in dry pyridine solution to react with the required quantity of benzyl alcohol also in dry pyridine, with cooling.

The reduction of these nitro-compounds to the corresponding amines was the next step in the process. The only known compound of this series is 2-aminobenzyl benzoate which has been described by Paul and Bodewig (*Ber.*, 1892, 25, 2062). The reduction was carried out either with alcoholic ammonium sulphide or aluminium-mercury couple in moist ether solution (Morgan and Burgess, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 697). The isolation of the reduction product of 4-nitrobenzyl benzoate is extremely difficult.

The preparation of the corresponding stibinic acids from these amino-esters necessitated particular care to prevent the hydrolysis of the ester grouping during the alkaline decomposition of the diazo-compound. An English Patent (813,058 of 1928) describes the preparation of aryl stibinic acids by a method, which, if successful, will render the preparation of these acids far less difficult and tedious. According to this patent, the additive compound obtained by treating a diazotised solution of amine in hydrochloric acid and antimony trichloride is dried and added to pyridine in small quantities at a time. On standing at ordinary temperature or warming on a water-bath between 60° and 70°, nitrogen is given off smoothly and on diluting with water, the aryl-stibinic acid is precipitated. But when attempts were made to prepare the stibinic acid from the amino-esters described in this communication by the above process, the products were not the expected compound but a brown resinous mass, completely insoluble in alkali, but which was found to contain antimony. The products were insoluble in all organic solvents including pyridine and could not be further purified.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Benzyl 2-Nitrobenzoate.—2-Nitrobenzoic acid (10 g.) and redistilled thionyl chloride (50 g.) were heated on a water-bath under reflux for 2 hours. The excess of thionyl chloride was then removed by heating under *vacuo* on a boiling water-bath. The residue in the flask was allowed to cool and then dissolved in pyridine (20 c.c.) which had previously been dried over anhydrous sodium carbonate. To a solution of benzyl alcohol (5.6 c.c.) in dry pyridine (10 c.c.) and cooled in ice, the acid chloride was added in small quantities at a time and thoroughly mixed after each addition. The reaction mixture became warm after each addition and was cooled in ice before

further addition was made. During the first stages of the reaction a yellowish-white solid separated which increased as more acid chloride was added, till after the addition of the whole the mixture became almost solid. The reaction vessel was then allowed to stand overnight in ice and then heated on a water-bath for 2 hours under reflux to complete the reaction. The hot liquid was then poured into crushed ice when a yellow oil separated which solidified after sometime. It crystallised from dilute methyl alcohol in glistening white plates, m.p. 54-55° (yield, 18 g.). (Found: N, 5.56. $C_{14}H_{11}O_4N$ requires N, 5.44 per cent.).

Benzyl 3-Nitrobenzoate.—The ester was prepared from 3-nitrobenzoic acid and thionyl chloride as described before. But the isolation of the ester was far more difficult.

When the hot pyridine solution, after the completion of the reaction, was poured into crushed ice, a thick yellow oil separated, which did not solidify even when cooled in a freezing mixture. On allowing to stand in a refrigerator overnight, a semi-solid mass was obtained. This was rapidly filtered off, dissolved in methyl alcohol, boiled with animal charcoal and filtered. The filtrate on cooling in a freezing mixture did not give any precipitate. On dilution, however, a light yellow oil was obtained, which on prolonged standing in a freezing mixture and scratching with a glass rod, solidified to a pale yellow solid. This was collected, washed with water and then with dilute sodium carbonate and again with water and then dried on a porous plate. The crystallisation of the compound was effected by dissolving it in methyl alcohol and then diluting with a small quantity of water when a yellow oil separated. The oil was then dissolved by warming the liquid and adding a small quantity of methyl alcohol. On cooling the solution in ice, the ester separated as white needles, m.p. 48-49° (yield, 12 g. from 10 g. of 3-nitrobenzoic acid). (Found: N, 5.67. $C_{14}H_{11}O_4N$ requires N, 5.44 per cent.).

Benzyl 4-Nitrobenzoate.—4-Nitrobenzoic acid (16.7 g.) and benzyl alcohol (10.8 c.c.) were heated on an oil-bath for 10 hours between 160° and 180°. On cooling the contents of the vessel solidified. The whole was taken up with rectified spirit, boiled with animal charcoal and filtered. The filtrate on cooling somewhat, deposited a certain quantity of a solid which was found to be a mixture of 4-nitrobenzoic acid and the required ester. This was filtered off and on diluting the filtrate the ester separated as white needles, m.p. 83-84° (yield, 25 g.).

2-Nitrobenzyl Benzoate.—This compound when prepared according to the method of Gomberg and Buchler (*loc. cit.*) was a light brown crystalline mass, m.p. 89-90°. But when prepared by the following method the m.p. was 101-2°.

2-Nitrobenzaldehyde (20 g.) was gradually added to a solution of caustic potash (10 g.) in water (80 c.c.) with cooling in ice and vigorous agitation after each addition of the aldehyde. It was found that the whole of the nitroaldehyde did not go into solution. The mixture was then allowed to stand for 3 days when a large quantity of needle-shaped crystals was found to have separated. The contents were then diluted with water (100 c.c.) when the solid dissolved. The alkaline liquid was then extracted thrice with ether, the ethereal layer separated and dried over ignited sodium sulphate overnight. On removing the ether, a light yellow liquid (2-nitrobenzyl alcohol) was left.

2-Nitrobenzyl alcohol was then condensed with benzoyl chloride in pyridine solution as described under the preparation of benzyl 2-nitrobenzoate. The crude product melted at 89-95°, but when twice recrystallised from absolute alcohol the m.p. rose to 101-2°. (Found: N, 5.57. $C_{14}H_{11}O_4N$ requires N, 5.44 per cent.).

3-Nitrobenzyl Benzoate.—3-Nitrobenzyl alcohol was prepared from 3-nitrobenzaldehyde as described above. The oil left after the evaporation of ether was dried by heating under vacuum on a boiling water-bath for 2 hours and left overnight. Phosphorus pentachloride (10 g.) was then gradually added to the dried oil in small portions. The reaction was very vigorous during the first stage but slackened off towards the end. Phosphorus oxychloride was then distilled off from a water-bath under reduced pressure. The residual oil, 3-nitrobenzyl chloride, amounted to 7 g.

The reaction between 3-nitrobenzyl chloride and sodium benzoate was carried out according to the method of Gomberg and Buchler (*loc. cit.*). To a solution of sodium benzoate (10 g. in 50 c.c. of water), 3-nitrobenzyl chloride (7 g.) was added and the mixture heated under reflux for 9 hours. On cooling a yellowish white solid separated. This was filtered off and twice recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 71-72° (yield, 8 g.). (Found: N, 5.64. $C_{14}H_{11}O_4N$ requires N, 5.44 per cent.).

4-Nitrobenzyl benzoate was similarly obtained from 4-nitrobenzyl chloride and sodium benzoate. The crude product was

crystallised from alcohol in light red prisms, m.p. 94-95°. (Found: N, 5.56. $C_{14}H_{11}O_4N$ requires N, 5.44 per cent.).

3-Nitrobenzoic Anhydride.—3-Nitrobenzoic acid (11 g.) was gradually mixed with phosphorus pentachloride (14 g.). After the first addition of the pentachloride the flask was slightly warmed but during the latter stages vigorous evolution of hydrochloric acid showed that the reaction was proceeding rapidly. Phosphorus oxychloride was then removed under reduced pressure (yield, 14 g.).

Benzyl alcohol (5.5 c.c.) was then added to the chloride prepared and cooled in ice. Caustic soda solution (10%) was then gradually added to the mixture of the alcohol and acid chloride, with violent agitation, till alkaline. A pasty mass was obtained which was filtered off, dried on a porous plate and then crystallised from benzene in yellowish-white, glistening plates, m.p. 162°—63°. (Found: C, 52.48; H, 2.8; N, 8.9. $C_{14}H_9O_7N_2$ requires C, 53.16; H, 2.6; N, 8.86 per cent.).

2-Nitrobenzoic Anhydride.—The preparation of the compound was carried out similarly employing thionyl chloride instead of phosphorus pentachloride. The solid product was crystallised from benzene in white needles, m.p. 128°-29°. (Found: N, 9.18. $C_{14}H_9O_7N_2$ requires N, 8.86 per cent.).

Benzyl 4-Aminobenzoate.

Benzyl 4-nitrobenzoate (10 g.) was dissolved in alcohol with warming, the solution cooled and saturated with dry ammonia gas for 1 hour. A slow stream of sulphuretted hydrogen was then passed through the solution for 4 hours which was then evaporated to dryness on a water-bath. The residue was taken up in alcohol and boiled for 2 hours under reflux with the addition of copper powder to remove sulphur. Copper sulphide was then filtered off and on diluting the filtrate a white crystalline solid separated. This was dried on a porous plate, dissolved in benzene and precipitated by the addition of a large excess of petroleum ether, filtered and dried in *vacuo* over liquid paraffin; m.p. 90—91°. (yield, 5.6 g.). (Found: N, 6.54. $C_{14}H_{13}O_2N$ requires N, 6.16 per cent.).

Benzyl 3-Aminobenzoate.—The nitro-compound was dissolved in alcohol and the reduction was carried out as described above. The residue obtained by evaporating the alcoholic liquid was repeatedly extracted with cold dilute hydrochloric acid, neutralised with dry

sodium carbonate, when a white emulsion was obtained. The whole was then extracted with ether, the ethereal layer dried over ignited sodium sulphate, and then evaporated to dryness. A yellow oily liquid remained which when treated with a few drops of dilute hydrochloric acid solidified. The solid was dissolved in alcohol and precipitated by the addition of a large excess of benzene, as white needles, m.p. 199-200°. (Found: N, 5.65. $C_{14}H_{14}O_2NCl$ requires N, 5.35 per cent.).

The substance is soluble in water, gives diazo-reaction and, with silver nitrate, a white precipitate of silver chloride. An alcoholic solution of the substance is distinctly acidic in reaction. All these show that the substance is the hydrochloride of benzyl 3-aminobenzoate.

Benzyl 2-Aminobenzoate.

The nitro-compound (5 g.) was dissolved in moist ether and treated with aluminium—mercury couple prepared from aluminium foil (8 g.) during 4 hours. During the progress of the reaction, the ether solution which was colourless at first, gradually assumed a pink colour. The reaction flask was then allowed to stand overnight, the sludge filtered off, washed with ether and dried over sodium sulphate. The dried ether solution was then treated with slow stream of dry hydrochloric acid, when a white solid separated. This was rapidly dried on a porous plate, dissolved in chloroform and precipitated with petroleum ether, as white needles m.p. 162-63° (yield, 2.5 g.). (Found: N, 4.98. $C_{14}H_{14}O_2NCl$ requires N, 5.35 per cent.).

The properties of the compound (*of. above*) show that the substance is not the free base but the hydrochloride.

2-Aminobenzyl Benzoate.—Attempts to prepare this compound according to the method of Paul and Bodewig (*loc. cit.*) were unsuccessful. The reduction was carried out as described for benzyl 2-nitrobenzoate. The crude product was crystallised by dissolving in chloroform and precipitating with petroleum ether. The product thus obtained had an m.p. 144-45°, identical with that described by Paul and Bodewig (*loc. cit.*).

3-Aminobenzyl benzoate was obtained from 3-nitrobenzyl benzoate in moist ether with aluminium—mercury couple. The reduction product was isolated by passing hydrochloric acid through the ether

solution. The crystallisation was effected by dissolving in alcohol and precipitating with ether, m.p. 198-99°. (Found: N, 5.4. $C_{14}H_{14}O_2NCl$ requires N, 5.35 per cent.).

The reduction of 4-nitrobenzyl benzoate was first carried out with hydrogen sulphide in ammoniacal alcoholic solution and the yellow liquid obtained after the removal of sulphur and evaporation of the solvent (alcohol) was left overnight in a vacuum desiccator. It was found that the yellow oil had been converted into a dark brown resinous mass which is insoluble in alcohol and fails to respond to the usual tests of amine. In moist ether solution, with aluminium—mercury couple, the nitro-body was smoothly converted into the amine but the isolation of the product proved to be futile. The oil that was obtained after evaporation of ether, decomposed into resinous mass as described before. On attempting to isolate the base as its hydrochloride from the ether solution (which was dried overnight over anhydrous sodium sulphate) by passing a current of dry hydrochloric acid gas, a white solid separated at first but it rapidly turned brown. This change of colour was so rapid that it was found impossible to prevent it. Attempts to isolate the hydrochloride from the brown mass were unsuccessful.

Preparation of Benzyl Benzoate-4-stibinate of Sodium.

Benzyl 4-aminobenzoate (4.4 g.) was added to well-cooled dilute hydrochloric acid (5 c.c. conc. acid. in 40 c.c. water) cooled in a freezing mixture and diazotised with sodium nitrite (1.5 g.). It was found that the whole of amine did not go into solution, though the solution was found to contain an excess of nitrous acid. The liquid was then rapidly filtered through a cold filter and the clear filtrate treated with a further quantity of cooled dilute hydrochloric acid (5 c.c.). Antimony trichloride prepared by dissolving antimony

trioxide (2 g.) in hydrochloric acid (15 c.c.) was added to the diazo-solution when a yellow precipitate separated. This was filtered off and a portion was dried on a porous plate.

The main portion was suspended in water, cooled to 5° and a dilute solution of caustic soda (5%) was added with vigorous agitation till faintly alkaline. During the addition, the temperature of the liquid was always kept below 10°. After the evolution of nitrogen had slackened off, the liquid was filtered off and the clear filtrate acidified with dilute sulphuric acid when the stibinic acid separated as a light brown gelatinous mass. This was allowed to settle and then filtered and washed free from sulphuric acid as far as possible. The mass was then suspended in water and dilute caustic soda solution added drop by drop till neutral and the solution evaporated to dryness in vacuum over sulphuric acid. The brown residue was then extracted with methyl alcohol, filtered and the filtrate treated with an excess of the ether when the sodium salt of the stibinic acid separated as a light yellow precipitate. This was filtered off, washed repeatedly with ether and then dried *in vacuo* over liquid paraffin. (Found: Sb, 30·7. $C_{14}H_{12}O_5SbNa$ requires Sb, 31·35 per cent.).

The portion of the additive product which had been dried on the porous plate was added to pyridine (25 c.c.) in small portions at a time. The colour of the pyridine changed first to yellow and then to red during the course of the addition and nitrogen was also given off. After the addition was complete, the liquid was warmed on a water-bath between 60° and 70° till the evolution of gas ceased. It was found that the whole of the solid did not pass into solution. The insoluble impurities were then filtered off and on diluting the clear pyridine solution, a brown pasty mass separated which was found to be insoluble in alkali. The brown mass was again dissolved in pyridine, heated on a water-bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour and then diluted: a brownish solid separated which was found to contain antimony but which was completely insoluble in dilute alkali and cannot be the expected stibinic acid. As further purification of the product was not possible, its identity could not be determined.

Benzyl benzoate-3-stibinate of sodium was obtained from the hydrochloride of benzyl 3-aminobenzoate, by the method already described. (Found: Sb, 30·34. $C_{14}H_{12}O_5SbNa$ requires Sb, 31·33 per cent.),

Benzyl Benzoate-2-stibinate of Sodium.

This was prepared from the hydrochloride of benzyl 2-amino-benzoate. (Found: Sb, 30.1. $C_{14}H_{12}O_5SbNa$ requires Sb, 31.33 per cent.).

Benzyl Benzoate-5'-stibinate of Sodium.

(Found: Sb, 30.58. $C_{14}H_{12}O_5SbNa$ requires Sb, 31.33 per cent.).

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DEPARTMENT OF APPLIED CHEMISTRY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY,
CALCUTTA.

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